

16 JOURNAL DIGITAL FORENSIC AND INDONESIA (2012-2022)

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Nim : 192040100039

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- The History of Forensic Linguistics as an Assisting Tool in the Analysis of Legal Terms
 - Journal Article | Open Access | Sriwijaya Law Review, Volume: 2, Issue: 2, Pages: 215-232. Jul 31, 2018
 - Authors: Houtman Houtman, Suryati Suryati
 - Citing Patents: 0 | Citing Scholarly Works: 1 | Reference Count: 0 | 067-380-693-943-800
 - 10.28946/slrev.vol2.iss2.135.pp215-233 | 230523503 | 2903838447 | LibKey | WorldCat
 - Additional Info: Open Access | Abstract | Full Text | Affiliation | Field of Study
 - Full Text match: Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung in 2011, Forensic linguistics was quite warmly spoken at that time ... linguistic work in Indonesia. According to its nature ... , so that the punishment of the aboriginal person was revoked. 2 In Indonesia, forensic linguistic
- A geographical analysis of trafficking on a popular darknet market.
 - Journal Article | Open Access | Forensic science international, Volume: 277, Pages: 88-102. Jun 4, 2017
 - Authors: Julian Broséus, Damien Rhumorbarbe, Marie Morelato, Ludovic Staehli, Quentin Rossy
 - Citing Patents: 0 | Citing Scholarly Works: 47 | Reference Count: 39 | Collections: 2 | 044-376-815-556-360
 - 10.1016/j.forsciint.2017.05.021 | 28624673 | 84057980 | 2620692324 | LibKey | WorldCat
 - Additional Info: Open Access | Abstract | Full Text | Affiliation | Field of Study | Published
 - Full Text match: Forensic Science International A geographical analysis of trafficking on a popular darknet ... Criminelles, University of Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland University ... illicit drug market through the analysis of digital, physical and chemical data. Forensic Sci. Int., 2016
- Determining the effective number and surfaces of teeth for forensic dental identification through the 3D point cloud data analysis
 - Journal Article | Open Access | Egyptian Journal of Forensic Sciences, Volume: 10, Issue: 1, Pages: 1-11. Feb 8, 2020
 - Authors: Arofi Kurniawan, Kouya Yodokawa, Moe Kosaka, Kaichi Ito, Keiichi Sasaki, Takafumi Aoki, Toshihiko Suzuki
 - Citing Patents: 0 | Citing Scholarly Works: 3 | Reference Count: 27 | 003-578-675-313-639
 - 10.1186/s41935-020-0181-z | 3031185305 | LibKey | WorldCat
 - Additional Info: Open Access | Abstract | Affiliation | Field of Study
- Requirement Specification to Develop Digital Health Promotion Platform for Millenial and Post-Millenial Generations in Surabaya Ind
 - Journal Article | Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology, Volume: 15, Issue: 2, Pages: 2022-2031. Apr 13, 2021
 - Authors: Atik Qurrota A Yunin Al-Isyrofi, Sri Widati, Rachmat Hargono
 - Citing Patents: 0 | Citing Scholarly Works: 1 | Reference Count: 0 | Collections: 1 | 022-648-346-967-244
 - 10.37506/ijfmt.v15i2.14661 | 3199033613 | LibKey | WorldCat
 - Additional Info: Abstract | Field of Study | Published

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- Subject Matter >
- Open Access >
- Query Tools >
- New Structured Search >

Critical issues in the historical and contemporary development of forensic anthropology in Australia: An international comparison.

Journal Article Open Access Forensic science international, Volume: 275, Mar 31, 2017
 Authors: Xanthé Mallett, Martin P Evison
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 5 Reference Count: 45 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1016/j.forsciint.2017.03.019 28449842 80693794
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Affiliation Published

Full Text match: and Contemporary Development of Forensic Anthropology in Australia: An International ... comparison. Forensic Science International, 275. 314.e1-31 Elsevier URL ... attacks in Bali, Indonesia, in Handbook of Forensic Anthropology and Archaeology, 2nd Ed., S. Blau

Validation of a standard forensic anthropology examination protocol by measurement of applicability and reliability on exhumed and biological attribution.

Journal Article Open Access Forensic science international, Volume: 279, Pages: 241-250, Sep 7, 2017
 Authors: Raffaella Arrabaca Francisco, Martin Evison, Moacyr Lobo da Costa Júnior, Teresa Cristina Pantozzi Silveira, José Marcelo Secchieri, Marco Aurélio Guimarães
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 3 Reference Count: 51 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1016/j.forsciint.2017.08.015 28926780 96783375 2752536960
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Funding Affiliation Field of Study Published

Full Text match: Validation of a standard forensic anthropology examination protocol by measurement of applicability ... and reliability on exhumed and archive san Forensic ... , M.L. da C., Silveira, T.C.P., Secchieri, J.M. and Guimarães, M.A. Validation of a standard forensic

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- Publisher >
- Subject Matter >
- Open Access >
- Query Tools >
- New Structured Search >

Empirical evaluation of spring powered air rifle storage and modifications on forensic practice and casework

Journal Article Open Access Forensic science international, Volume: 294, Pages: 160-172, Nov 16, 2018
 Authors: Kate J Greenslade, Rachel Bolton-King
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 0 Reference Count: 21 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1016/j.forsciint.2018.11.004 30576900 161771265 2901879854
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Affiliation Field of Study Published

Full Text match: and modifications on forensic practice and casework Authors: Kate J. Greenslade (Conceptualization) (Methodology ... storage and modifications on Greenslade1 & Rachel S. ... Bolton-King" a Department of Criminal Justice & Forensic Science, Staffordshire University, Leek Road

Ethical Awareness, Ethical Judgment and Whistleblowing: A Moderated Mediation Analysis

Journal Article Open Access Journal of Business Ethics, Volume: 155, Issue: 1, Pages: 289-304, Apr 18, 2017
 Authors: Hengky Latan, Charbel José Chiappetta Jabbour, Ana Beatriz Lopes de Sousa Jabbour
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 42 Reference Count: 87 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1007/s10551-017-3534-2 62919531 286355892 2606764625
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Affiliation Field of Study

Full Text match: J is a digital archive of University of Strathclyde research outputs. It has been developed ... of Accounting, STIE Bank BPD Jateng, Jl. Pemuda No 4A, Se Consulting, Jl ... Kertanegara Selatan V No.5B, Semarang, 50241 Indonesia (3) Stirling Management School, Centre

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- Subject Matter >
- Open Access >
- Query Tools >
- New Structured Search >

Business unusual: collective action against bribery in international business

Journal Article Open Access Crime, Law and Social Change, Volume: 71, Issue: 2, Pages: 151-170, Nov 6, 2017
 Authors: Elizabeth David-Barrett
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 1 Reference Count: 53 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1007/s10611-017-9715-1 96839864 2756389349
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Funding Affiliation Field of Study

Full Text match: in Nigeria, Argentina and Indonesia, building coalitions with government bodies, international ... supporting the provision of training on the new regu digital record ... ministries and ports. In Indonesia, its project to end corruption in customs clearance in the port

Internationalizing the study of gang membership : validation issues from Latin America

Journal Article Open Access British Journal of Criminology, Volume: 57, Issue: 5, Pages: 1165-1184, Jul 21, 2016
 Authors: Juan Antonio Rodríguez, Neelie Pérez Santiago, Christopher Birkbeck, Freddy Crespo, Solbey Morillo
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 4 Reference Count: 45 Collections: 1 LibKey WorldCat
 10.1093/bjc/azw058 42590441 2497007528
 Additional Info: Open Access Abstract Full Text Field of Study

Full Text match: This version is available at: http://usir.salford.ac.uk/39363/ Published Date 2016 USIR is a digital ... two Latin American countries (Brazil, Venezuela), Internationalising the Study ... Springer. French, D., Pidada, S., and Victor, A. (2005), "Friendships of Indonesian and United States

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Cyber warfare and autonomous self-defence

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *Journal on the Use of Force and International Law*, Volume: 4, Issue: 2, Pages: 312-343. Jun 23, 2017
 Authors: Francis Grimal, Jae Sundaram
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 0 Reference Count: 0 Collections: 1 [005-188-834-221-993](#)
[10.1080/20531702.2017.1338877](#) [80682985](#) [2618824544](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
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Full Text match: *to legitimate software, such as digital certificates, while using a self-launching programme, allowed its ... of sustained digital attacks on 26 April 2007 continued for over two weeks, covering ... Markoff, 'Digital Fears Emerge after Data Siege in Estonia,' The New York Times, 29 May 2007*

Correction to: Gravity in the Statute of the International Criminal Court and Cyber Conduct That Constitutes, Instigates or Facilitates I Crimes

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *Criminal Law Forum*, Volume: 30, Issue: 3, Pages: 247-272. Jun 1, 2019
 Authors: Marco Roscini
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 0 Reference Count: 0 Collections: 1 [060-090-720-974-961](#)
[10.1007/s10609-019-09370-0](#) [200197846](#) [2947705140](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
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Full Text match: *Threat Matrix of Digital Espionage, Crime, and Warfare (New York: Penguin Press, 2011), p. 32). 43 ...)). MARCO ROSCINI258 digital forensics for its Sci to improve its ability to collect ... and analyse digital evidence.45 Having said that, at the preliminary stage the standard of proof*

Exploring alternative terrain in the rehabilitation and treatment of offenders: Findings from a prison-based music project

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *Journal of Offender Rehabilitation*, Volume: 55, Issue: 6, Pages: 396-418. Jul 5, 2016
 Authors: Laura Caulfield, Dean J Wilkinson, David Wilson
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 12 Reference Count: 24 Collections: 1 [003-721-488-365-846](#)
[10.1080/10590674.2016.1194943](#) [42595539](#) [2472205337](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
 Additional Info: [Open Access](#) [Abstract](#) [Full Text](#) [Affiliation](#) [Field of Study](#) [Published](#)

Full Text match: *Indonesia that has been identified as suitable for community or group settings; it has an informal ... as a group. They also learn about Indonesian cult art forms (e.g. shadow ... public place in the community. Interviews were digitally recorded and transcribed. - Offender*

Decoding Article 8 of the International Law Commission's Articles on State Responsibility: Attribution of Cyber Operations by Non-State Actors

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *Journal of Conflict and Security Law*, Volume: 21, Issue: 3, Pages: 405-428. Sep 25, 2016
 Authors: Kubo Mañák
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 8 Reference Count: 0 Collections: 1 [067-984-283-608-644](#)
[10.1093/jcsl/krw014](#) [77031583](#) [2517510945](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
 Additional Info: [Open Access](#) [Abstract](#) [Full Text](#) [Field of Study](#)

Full Text match: *States Use Hackers To Do Digital Dirty Work' illustrate that outsourcing of this kind has now ... : States Use Hackers To Do Digital Dirty Work', Financie 2015) digital forensic data as well as a combination of intelligence sources*

Southern Criminology

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *British Journal of Criminology*, Volume: 56, Issue: 1, Pages: 1-20. Aug 20, 2015
 Authors: Kerry Carrington, Russell Hogg, Máximo Sozzo
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 221 Reference Count: 44 Collections: 1 [153-818-463-122-733](#)
[10.1093/bjcr/azv083](#) [33502601](#) [W4214504696](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
 Additional Info: [Open Access](#) [Abstract](#) [Full Text](#) [Field of Study](#)

Full Text match: *North and South. The global digital divide is closing even more rapidly, shrinking the world ... across the Muslim majority countries of Libya, Sudan, Al Palestine, Algeria, Somalia*

July 2013: Editorial Note

Journal Article [Open Access](#) *Family Court Review*, Volume: 51, Issue: 3, Pages: 345-349. Aug 22, 2013
 Authors: Andrew Schepard
 Citing Patents: 0 Citing Scholarly Works: 1 Reference Count: 0 Collections: 8 [019-141-612-551-436](#)
[10.1111/fcre.12031](#) [55330012](#) [2321027170](#) [LibKey](#) [WorldCat](#)
 Additional Info: [Open Access](#) [Abstract](#) [Full Text](#) [Affiliation](#) [Field of Study](#) [Published](#)

Full Text match: *the leader in the nation in digital technology," Morales said. Under his leadership, Carl Sandburg ... College was named No. 1 in the nation for digital community colleges its size ... , Litigation Support Partner Palm Springs, CA 92262 12 Palm Springs & Forensic Accounting, Accounting*